

MOBILE LEARNING WITH CASE STUDY METHODS FOR CIVIC EDUCATION IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This development research produces learning media in the form of mobile learning with a case study method for Civic Education subjects. This development is expected to facilitate students learning in class VI and form characters that follow the values of Pancasila. This development uses the Rapid Prototyping model, which consists of five stages: assess needs and analyze content, set objectives, construct a prototype, utilize the prototype, and install and maintain the System. The evaluation in this development research consisted of expert reviews (material experts and media experts) and user trials. The assessment involved a material "very good," a media expert, and 12 users. The results of the expert review stated that mobile learning was excellent by material experts and media experts. Meanwhile, at the evaluation stage of one-on-one trials and group trials, it was noted that mobile learning was excellent. So it can be concluded that mobile learning with this case study method is "very good" and can be used for learning media with further improvements.

Keywords: Mobile Learning, Metode Studi Kasus, Sekolah Dasar, Rapid Prototyping

1 INTRODUCTION

Pancasila is the foundation (Wen Lee & Ande, 2022) and guidelines for the Indonesian people in daily life in society and the state (Diniyanto & Sutrisno, 2022). The majority of Indonesian citizens certainly already know what is contained in Pancasila. In practice, many cases and irregularities in Indonesia still do not follow the contents of Pancasila (Mukaromah et al., 2022). Many cases occur among students who show that the character possessed by students is contrary to the application of Pancasila, one of which is the case of bullying. Bullying is a negative behavior from a person or group toward victims who are targeted to be hurt physically or emotionally, either verbally, physically, relationally, or cyber (Kallman et al., 2021). The results of the PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) research in 2018 showed that the number of bullying that occurred among students in Indonesia reached 41% (Safari, 2022). This figure also makes Indonesia the fifth country with the highest number of student bullying cases (Ramadhanti & Hidayat, 2022). Cases of bullying or bullying are rampant in Indonesia and take various forms, ranging from students receiving threats and ridicule to violence (Filipenko et al., 2022). Another source also stated that bullying occurs mainly in elementary school students aged 7-12 years, accounting for 76% of bullying cases reported to the Indonesian National Commission for Child Protection (Borualogo & Casas, 2021a).

Cases that contradict the values of Pancasila also occur in one of the public elementary schools in the Bekasi Regency area. The researcher interviewed sixth-grade teachers at SDN Telajung 01. The teacher said that many cases in elementary school, especially in grade VI, contradicted the application of Pancasila values. Some of these cases are cases of bullying that happened to a grade VI student several years ago. The student received unpleasant treatment from some of his classmates because he did not have the appearance of his peers and worked as a tire patcher to help his family's economy. This problem shows that students, as part of Indonesian society, have forgotten their national identity, which should be based on Pancasila, especially on the second principle. In the second principle of Pancasila, we sued to respect and treat fellow human beings fairly and civilly (Tirza, 2022). They followed their dignity without discriminating against ethnicity, religion, gender, social position, and skin tone because all Indonesian citizens have equality of status, degree, rights, and essential obligations as creatures of God Almighty. In this precept, human values must uphold social life (Filipenko et al., 2022). The empathy and compassion to act pretty without using violence should be more instilled in the younger generation (Iriani & Astuti, 2021) to reduce the level of bullying from an early age, namely at the sixth-grade elementary school level which is the age of early teens (12-15 years). In adolescence, children begin to learn and develop in terms of recognizing themselves and their environment. Changing students' character is more complicated than instilling character values from an early age that follow the Pancasila values to create moral and dignified characters (Filipenko et al., 2022). Pancasila and Citizenship Education aims to develop people who believe, have a noble character, and have a high sense of responsibility following Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution (Fadil & Rahmawati, 2022). Citizenship Education is a process to prepare a generation that knows its responsibilities as citizens (Noe et al., 2021). However, it is miserable that so far, the Civic Education subjects, which contain the delivery of Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution, are not the fundamental values of national and state life but are only limited to the basis of government administration.

Based on interviews with sixth-grade teachers, information was obtained that Civic Education activities were not optimal. Students are less interested in Civic Education and think it is a complex subject because it is theoretical and rote. In addition, the lecture method still dominates learning activities, and teachers only rely on printed learning books which eventually causes students to become bored when learning takes place. The lack of student interest and the use of conventional learning methods also causes a lack of student participation and activity in the learning process

because students only listen and accept the material presented by the teacher without trying to understand it more deeply, either by asking directly to the teacher or seeking information independently. In face-to-face learning activities, students still have difficulty participating in learning, plus now learning activities at all levels of education in Indonesia in the past year have been carried out remotely. It also causes the learning process at SDN Telajung 01 not to run optimally.

Civic Education that only relies on media in the form of printed learning books and is dominated by verbalism will make it challenging to achieve learning objectives. Moreover, the examples and applications of this Civic Education are still abstract. This condition, if left unchecked, will lead to failure in achieving Civic Education objectives which should be able to form students who behave and have character, according to Pancasila. Civic Education should be able to involve students to play an active role, such as the concept of active learning, which should minimize the part of the teacher towards the use of learning media that can actualize the learning process to be more efficient, effective, and practical (Winarni et al., 2022). Civic Education activities that focus on forming student attitudes and characters should also be presented in the right way and with suitable media so that Civic Education can make students not only able to memorize theories but also be able to apply them in real life.

Based on these problems, a solution is needed that can be used to help achieve the learning objectives. The answer is the selection and use of appropriate learning methods assisted by learning media that can facilitate the achievement of predetermined learning objectives. The learning method that can be used in Civic Education is the case study method. The case study method is a form of inquiry that focuses on solving problems or cases. This method is closely related to problem-solving learning, but this case study method has a broader scope (Winarni et al., 2022). The case study method can assist students in making decisions regarding problems in real stud lives.

The results of Muhammad Japar'sents research show that the case study method in Civic Education activities can facilitate students to think critically, analyze, and act following the Pancasila. Learning using the case study method will present problems relevant to events that have been experienced or will occur in students' daily lives. Several types of cases include (1) directed case, (2) dilemma (decision case), (3) interrupted case (4) analysis or issue case. And the case that will be used in this research is the analysis or issue case (Japar, 2018). While the learning media that can be a solution to the problems above is mobile learning. Mobile learning is a model that utilizes digital technology media that can be an alternative to learning media that has high enough flexibility, allowing users to

access information, materials, and instructions quickly, and can also be used anywhere and anytime (Widyatama & Pratama, 2022).

Online learning in higher education is increasingly needed (Aswan, 2022; Pattaufi & Aswan, 2022; Thaib et al., 2017). This need makes many lecturers try to develop online learning processes, both blended learning, online learning, and Mobile Learning (Arnidah et al., 2022; Arriany & Aswan, 2022; Siregar & Aswan, 2019). Mobile learning is a learning model that adopts the development of cellular technology and mobile devices (handphones) used as learning media. Mobile learning was developed with a multimedia format that presents text, images, and audio and minimizes video and animation due to the limited content size so that it is easily accessible via cellphone so that it becomes exciting and easy-to-understand learning material (Hardiansyah et al., 2022; Jurnal et al., 2022). Using mobile learning as a learning tool can make teaching activities easier because it can stimulate students outside school hours or face-to-face (Prima et al., 2022). Using mobile phones, students can access learning materials in text, images, sound, data, and video (Hardiansyah et al., 2022). In this research, mobile learning will be developed as a software application. Mobile learning is suitable to be used independently by students because mobile devices have been widely used among students who are a generation of digital natives. It's supported by a survey of internet users in Indonesia in 2019-2020, reaching 196.7 million users from Indonesia's population of 266,911,900 people (Triwibowo et al., 2022). The rapid number of internet users, including elementary school students, opens up the potential for developing and using mobile learning to help smooth learning. Mobile devices used in mobile learning include PDAs, cell phones, and tablets. With the existence of digital learning media in the form of mobile learning, learning is expected to be more interesting because there are variations in teaching media so that it does not only rely on printed learning books and teacher descriptions so that students can feel new experiences in Civic Education. Another advantage of mobile learning is the use of smaller devices that are mobile and cheaper than devices such as personal computers. Learning materials contained in mobile learning can also be visualized with a more attractive appearance and can be combined with content suitable for various student learning styles.

Based on the description above will be developed a product in the form of mobile learning media using case study methods that are interactive, communicative, and fun. Learning materials will be presented through sound, text, pictures, videos, examples of applications and cases following everyday life, and practice questions related to learning materials that can arouse students' intellectual emotions. The difference between this development and previous developments is that case studies

and mobile learning methods can be used remotely to support Civic Education, especially in materials that aim to shape students' attitudes and character. Mobile learning can also be used offline, so students don't need an internet connection. It can re-instill the values of Pancasila in students and help the smooth learning process of teachers and students. In addition, it is expected to create independence in students when using these media.

2 METHODOLOGY

This type of product development research uses the Rapid Prototyping development model. The model consists of 5 stages, namely (Pratiwi et al., 2022) :

(1) Assess Needs & Analyze Content

At the assessment needs stage, the goal is to identify the needs and characteristics of students and their needs during learning. Meanwhile, at the Analyze Content stage, an analysis of the material to be delivered is carried out, the learning media to be used, and the duration of the delivery of learning materials.

(2) Set Objectives

The next stage is the formulation of learning objectives that must be discussed with related material experts. The learning objectives will formulate general learning objectives that include the main learning objectives. Then develop specific objectives which contain derivatives of the general purposes that have been acquired. The formulation of this goal is based on the analysis results in the first stage.

(3) Construct a Prototype

At this stage, a prototype for developing student analysis results, learning materials, and formulations is made. The steps in making this prototype is creating a content map, designing scripts, developing content, and developing usage procedures.

(4) Utilize Prototype

After the prototype has been developed, a review of material experts, learning media experts, and student trials as users is carried out. The prosecution is rapid, where adjustments or revisions will be made to each feedback received.

(5) Install & Maintain Systems.

This research produces mobile learning that has been re-exported into .apk form, ready to be installed and used on mobile smartphone devices. At this stage, revisions are made based on feedback from expert reviews of material and media experts as well as input from students. Corrections are made until the product is suitable for use.

The target users in this study are class VI students at SDN Telajung 01. The implementation of this research was carried out from January 2021 to November 2021. Products developed will go through formative evaluation with expert reviews, one-to-one user testing, small group user tests, and evaluation of learning outcomes. This development uses a questionnaire instrument with a Likert scale of 4-1. The aspects assessed are adjusted to the theory of computer and software product quality, characteristics and criteria for learning media assessment, product assessment, and graphic design principles.

3 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Result

The implementation of this development research is carried out online and offline. The development was carried out for ten months, from January 2021 to November 2021. This development uses the Rapid Prototyping development model by Tripp Bichelmeyer 1990. The following are the stages of development:

1) Assess Needs & Analyze Content

a) Assess Needs

Based on the interview guide to teachers that had been made, the teacher said that Civic Education activities in class VI of SDN Telajung 01 were still using the lecture method. In addition, the media used in learning activities is in the form of printed books. Student learning outcomes in Civics Education to Pancasila are still not optimal. It is based on the students' daily tests, which show that the score is still below the KKM. One meeting on the subject of Civics on a theme of 35 minutes duration. The teacher revealed that students felt bored when learning Civic Education and were less interested in Civics lessons. The obstacles students face in the Civic Education process are that students perceive Civics as only theoretical and memorizing. The limited learning media and the methods used to make it difficult for students to understand the abstract Civics material. For the

characteristics of students in class VI of SDN Telajung, students are already able to use the device independently, which is a consideration in developing media according to the ability of these students.

b) Analyze Content

At this stage, information is obtained regarding the Civics Education material that will be developed. The results obtained after discussing with the teacher and looking at the books used by students are that the fabric used in the development this time is related to the values of the second precept of Pancasila. The material is contained in the Civics Class VI subject on Theme 7 Sub-theme 1 (Leadership material for Leaders Around Me). The material in the theme book is still incomplete because it only presents the points of the second principle of Pancasila according to the TAP MPR, and there is no further explanation or example. The values of the second principle of Pancasila and their application need to be made into mobile learning media because currently, learning is being carried out remotely (PJJ) and does not get direct explanations from the teacher. So it is hoped that it will make it easier for students to understand the material even though they are learning from home.

2) Set Objectives

After conducting a needs assessment and content analysis, in the second stage, activities were carried out to set learning objectives for mobile learning, which were developed by discussing with the teacher. After using mobile learning, the general instructional purpose is that students are expected to be able to analyze the application of the values of the second precept of Pancasila in everyday life. While the Special Instructional Objectives are (1) Students are expected to be able to explain the points contained in the second principle of Pancasila, (2) Students are expected to be able to mention examples of the application of the second principle of Pancasila, (3) Students are expected to be able to analyze case examples of the application of the second principle of Pancasila.

3) Construct a Prototype

The next stage is developing a mobile learning prototype. This third stage starts with creating the design of the prototype to be developed. The design stages include producing GBIM (Outline of Media Content), JM (Material Outline), flowchart, and storyboard.

a) Making GBIM, JM, Flowchart, and Storyboard

The Media Outline (GBIM) and Material Outline (JM) are produced at this stage. The GBIM and JM are included in the appendix. After the GBIM and JM were made, the developer started to make flowcharts and storyboards based on the previously created GBIM and JM. The purpose of making flowcharts and storyboards is as an illustration or illustration that will be presented in the software used in developing mobile learning (Smart Apps Creator). Flowcharts and storyboards will be used as references in the development of mobile learning, also included in the appendix.

b) Making Prototype

At this stage, the design display and components of the collection and material will be presented in the mobile learning prototype. The design was produced using Adobe Illustrator. The following is an example of creating a display and content design using Adobe Illustrator.

Figure 1 Mobile Learning Development Process on Smart Apps Creator Software

Figure 2 Mobile Learning Main Page Display

Figure 3 Pages of Sample Case Materials for the Second Precept of Pancasila

4) Utilize prototype

a) Expert Review Stage

The expert review aims to assess the material contained in mobile learning.

Table 1 Recapitulation of Expert Review Results

Respondents	Average score
Material Expert	3,68
Learning Media Expert	3,40
Average Value	3,54

After receiving reviews from media and material experts, the developer carried out revision activities on mobile learning following comments and inputs provided by experts.

b) One-to-One Trial Phase

One-to-one or one-to-one trials were conducted on two sixth-grade students at SDN Telajung 01. The two students were chosen because they had different levels of understanding. From the results of these trials, the average score is as follows:

Table 2 Recapitulation of One-to-One Trial Results

Respondents	Average score
Respondent 1	3.53
Respondent 2	3.03
Average Value	3.28

c) Small-Group Trial Phase

After the one-to-one trial was carried out, the next thing to do was a small group trial consisting of 10 students with different bits of intelligence. The results of these trials are as follows:

Figure 4 Small Group Trial Results Recapitulation

Furthermore, an assessment of student learning outcomes is carried out by being given an evaluation of learning outcomes. The following are the results of the review:

Figure 5 Recapitulation of Learning Outcome Evaluation

5) Install and Maintain System

The step taken at this last stage is to export the final results of the revised mobile learning. Mobile learning that has been shipped back into .apk form is ready to be installed and used on smartphone mobile devices.

Discussion

Pancasila is the basis of the state (Wen Lee & Ande, 2022) and the way of life of the Indonesian people. However, many cases and irregularities in Indonesia are still not by the values of Pancasila (Mukaromah et al., 2022). An example is bullying. The study's results stated that 58.35 male students had been victims of bullying, while 67.8% of female students had been victims of bullying (Krisnana et al., 2021). Another source also stated that bullying mainly occurs in elementary school students aged 7-12 years, accounting for 76% of bullying cases reported to the National Commission for Child Protection (Borualogo & Casas, 2021b). Cases of bullying also occurred in one of the public elementary schools in the Bekasi Regency area, such as at SDN Telajung 01. This problem shows that students, as part of Indonesian society, have forgotten their national identity, which should be based on Pancasila, especially on the second principle. In the second principle of Pancasila, we must respect and treat fellow human beings in a fair and civilized manner (Tirza, 2022) by their dignity without distinction of ethnicity, religion, gender, social position, skin color, and so on.

Knowledge and application of Civics values must be improved to avoid deviating further. The lack of student interest and the use of conventional learning methods also cause students to become

passive in the learning process. Solutions are needed that can be used to help achieve learning objectives. Online learning, where the learning process can be done on a mobile basis anywhere and anytime with various platforms, can improve students' understanding and learning outcomes (Aritonang & Safitri, 2021; Aswan, 2018; Taskiran, 2021). Mobile Learning is a learning process that can be an alternative to improve student understanding in the learning process (Pillena et al., 2019; Talakua & Sesca Elly, 2020). PKN learning using mobile learning is effective and can improve student learning outcomes, with 86% of students getting results above the minimum (Lestari & Halimi, 2022; Nurzaelani & Kasman, 2019; Sarkadi et al., 2020). Increasing knowledge of PKN is expected to affect the attitudes of students so that they do not do things that are contrary to Pancasila (Aydin & Yildirim, 2021; Hudi, 2017) Aydin & Yildirim, 2021; Hudi, 2017)

4 CONCLUSION

The product produced in this development research is mobile learning with a case study method for Civic Education for class VI at an elementary school at SDN Telajung 01. This mobile learning was developed using the Rapid Prototyping model, which consists of 5 stages: Assess Needs & Analyze Content, Set Goals, Build Prototypes, Utilize Prototypes and Install & Maintain Systems. This product has undergone a formative evaluation, resulting in a media expert review of 3.4 and a material expert of 3.68. Meanwhile, the One to one user trial got a score of 3.4, the small group user trial was 3.4, and the evaluation of learning outcomes with an average value of 90. These results indicate that mobile learning with the case study method can be categorized as very good and suitable to be used as a Civic Education media. Mobile learning with the case study method for Civic Education for Class VI subjects has several shortcomings in its development. Improvements need to continue to be made to improve again so that it can maximize use. Therefore, several suggestions can be considered for the necessary repair materials.

It can be even better for developers to perform maintenance and repairs to improve the quality of mobile learning so they can do mobile learning. More parties can feel the value of its usefulness for further developers who will develop mobile learning so that they can master things related to the development of good mobile learning, such as programming languages , or consult with experts in the field of making software for mobile learning. In addition, developers also need to understand how to create mobile learning that can be used on various mobile/mobile device operating systems.

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